

A Study on Challenges and Opportunities of Women Entrepreneurs

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Abstract

It is now widely accepted that if national development has to be purposeful and relevant, women have to be full-fledged participants in economic activities. The development of women as entrepreneurs will generate multifaceted socio-economic benefit to the country. Participation of women in economic activities is now emerging as a universal phenomenon. The women entrepreneurs are motivated to a higher level. They have accepted the problems as challenge in their career. Today there is a greater awakening among women. Given an opportunity, they will deliver the results.

Introduction

For developing countries like India, women entrepreneurship is of vital necessity to achieve rapid, all-round and regionally and socially balanced economic growth. It is now widely accepted that if national development has to be purposeful and relevant, women have to be full-fledged participants in economic activities. The development of women as entrepreneurs will generate multifaceted socio-economic benefit to the country. Participation of women in economic activities is now emerging as universal phenomenon.

Reasons has identified the following reasons for the women entering business

1. Women who take entrepreneurship becomes of economic needs.
2. Women with a family background in some skill or trade and desire to earn extra income.
3. Women with personality characteristics such as need for achievement.
4. Women, who take it up as leisure time activity.
5. On official advice and guidance.

Development of Women Entrepreneurs

Development of women entrepreneurship should form an integral part all development efforts. In the seventh five year plan, integration of women in development process was suggested through the following means,

1. Treat women as special target group in all development programmes.
2. Diversify vocational training facilities for women to suit their varied needs and skills.
3. Encourage appropriate technologies for reducing their drudgery and increasing productivity.
4. Provide marketing assistance at the state level.
5. Increase women's participation in decisions making.

Schemes

Rural women entrepreneurs are assisted under the following schemes:

1. Self- Help-Groups (SHGs)

It plays a vital role in rural development, In India, the banking sectors has formally accepted SHGs as eligible entities for development of credit. The success of SHG financing is based on self-trust and self-help. It performs a member of useful functions as follows.

- Enabling members to become self-dependent and self-reliant.
- Providing a forum for member for discussing their social and economic problems.
- Providing a platform for member for exchange of ideas.
- Fostering a spirits of self-help and co-operation among members.
- Instilling in members the strength and confidence for solving problems.
- Providing organizational strength to members.

2. National Alliance of Young Entrepreneurs (NAYE)

It has been a pioneer in promotion and development of entrepreneurship among women. It set up a women's wing in 1975. The women entrepreneurs are assisted by women's wing of NAYE as follows:

- Getting better access to capital, infrastructure and markets.
- Development of management and production capabilities.
- Identifying investment opportunities.

3. Development of Women and Children in Rural Areas (DWCRA)

It is a women component of IRDP. It was launched by the in 1982. With the objective of focusing attention on women below poverty line.

The specific objectives DWCRA as follows

- Achieve significant growth in income of poor women.
- Make women organize themselves to meet their identified needs, and
- Improve existing services and resources through activities, complement supplement and make the best use of what already exist.

Objectives of the study

The study analyzed the challenges and opportunities of women entrepreneurs in the districts of Pudukkottai from various angles and offers useful suggestions to overcome these inherent challenges.

Methodology

Methodology of any type of research study takes a vital role in bringing a logical and scientific approach. It requires a strong base to the research and it leads to a reliable as well as valid interpretations. Pudukkottai District is the geographical area of the study. In this district, the Women Entrepreneurs are running in large extent and they have been selected for this research.

Table 1
Analysis of Demographic Environment

S.No.	Attitude/variable	Classification	No. of Respondent	Total
1.	Marital Status	Married	330(66)	500
		Unmarried	170(34)	
2.	Age Group (in years)	Up to 20	50(10)	500
		20-40	270(54)	
		40-60	95(19)	
		60&above	85(17)	
3.	Educational Qualification	Illiterate	24(4.8)	500
		School Level	186(37.2)	
		College Level	220(44.0)	
		Technical Level	70(14.0)	
4.	Occupation	Employee	140(28)	500
		Agriculture	260(52)	
		Business	30(6)	
		Unemployed	70(14)	
5.	Annual Income (in Rs.)	Upto 25,000	410(82)	500
		25,000-50,000	70(14)	
		50,000 & above	20(4)	
6.	Area of Residence	Village	180(36)	500
		Town	220(44)	
		City	100(20)	

Source: Primary data

Inference

The Table-1 reveals that the majority of the respondents are involved in the Women Entrepreneurs between the age groups of 20- 40 and they constituted 54 per cent and the same way the least per cent of age groups of above 60 ages. The study theme explain us about the education wise respondent are participated in the Women Entrepreneurs. The result reveals that the majority of the respondents are involved in the Women Entrepreneurs college level and they constituted 44 per cent, and lease percentages of 4.8 percent of respondents are only illiterate. It reveals that the majority of the respondents are married they constituted 66 per cent.

The Occupational status of respondents in the Women Entrepreneurs is one of the important parts of the research result theme so the results indicating the 52 percent of respondents are agricultural activities. It mainly concluded that the majority of the respondents are depending in agricultural occupations. (Entrepreneurial activities are petty shops, flower shops, tailoring, fish sales, tea shops, hotel business, textiles, general stores, milk business, chalk making, mini mill operating, floriculture, ceramic and cashew nuts business etc.)

The study reveals that majority of the respondent are involved in the Women Entrepreneurs below Rs.25,000 annual income group and majority of the respondent area of residence are town.

Findings of the Study

The major findings of the study are as follows:

1. The majority of the respondents are involved in the Women Entrepreneurs between the age groups of 20- 40 and they constituted 54 per cent.
2. Majority of the respondents are involved in the Women Entrepreneurs college level and they constituted 44 per cent.
3. Majority of the respondents are married they constituted 66 per cent.
4. Majority of the respondents are depending in agricultural occupations.
5. Majority of the respondent are involved in the Women Entrepreneurs below Rs.25,000 annual income group.
6. Majority of the respondent area of residence are town.

Suggestions

Some important suggestions are as follows. The following steps need to be undertaken to have a successful macro as well as at micro level so as to create an entrepreneurial environment in the region.

- Formation of a district level apex body.
- Identification of prospective entrepreneurs, creation of SHGs micro enterprises.
- The Government can give relaxation for giving assistance to the Women Entrepreneurs,
- The Government can conduct many Entrepreneurship programmes in order to give technical knowledge, to increase the self-confidence of the Women Entrepreneur etc.
- The loan amounts which are borrowed from different banks for the development of activities in the SHGs, should be repaid regularly at the fixed rate of interest which was better relationship with the banks and the government.

Conclusion

In this study we have assessed the importance of women's entrepreneurship. Thus, it is entrepreneurship serves as a catalyst of economic development. On the whole, the role of women entrepreneurs in economic development of a country can best be put as "An economy is the effect for which entrepreneurship is the cause". Women entrepreneurs have become a strong driving force in today's corporate world. Not only are they able to equalize their duties of both motherhood and half of all businesses owned today. Husbands played a major role in career development of married women entrepreneurs. This is a positive change in the attitude of husbands not only to accept their wives earning, but also guiding and supporting them to run their own enterprise. The women entrepreneurs are motivated to a higher level. They have accepted the problems as challenge in their career. Today there is a greater awakening among women. Given an opportunity, they will deliver the results.

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